

1 **What fMRI studies say about the nature of the psychedelic effect: a scoping**
2 **review**

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14

15 **Abstract**

16 Research on psychedelic drugs, such as psilocybin, LSD or DMT, is a burgeoning field,
17 with an increasing number of studies showing their promise in treatment of mental disorders as
18 well as examining their mechanism of action. Determining their effect on the brain is crucial from
19 clinical standpoint, but also offers highly promising avenues of advancement in basic neuroscience
20 - functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) is one of the most useful techniques to do so,
21 with a number of newly published studies increasing every year. Here we present a scoping review
22 of existing fMRI studies of serotonergic psychedelics to date, with a focus on finding unifying
23 themes among them, in order to comprehensively grasp current directions within this field. We
24 cluster the existing studies by fMRI modality and find several lines of developing concepts
25 complementing the established models of psychedelic actions on the brain: namely, we describe a
26 general picture of de-differentiation with the default mode network at its core captured by a diverse
27 array of different techniques, complex changes to the thalamus, amygdala and medial temporal
28 lobe structures, and the importance of the phenomenon of ego dissolution. Finally, contrasts to
29 phenomenologically similar states and the successful process of anchoring fMRI findings to other
30 markers are discussed.

31

32 1 Introduction

33 The research into psychedelics is undergoing a resurgence. Accumulating clinical data
34 point to a great potential of these substances in treatment of a range of psychiatric disorders. If
35 proven effective, psychedelic drugs would provide a sorely needed addition to the armamentarium
36 of psychiatric therapies, which currently still remain inadequate for an unacceptably large portion
37 of patients – as an example, in a respected study for treatment of depression, a full third of patients
38 didn't achieve remission (Gaynes et al. 2009). Psychedelics with their radically different
39 mechanism of action thus present an opportunity to narrow or even fill this gap. Not just in
40 treatment-resistant depression - research shows promise in addictions, OCD, existential distress in
41 terminal conditions (Nichols 2016), anorexia nervosa (Peck et al. 2023), depressive episodes in
42 type II bipolar disorder (Aaronson et al. 2024), and even beyond psychiatry as in migraine
43 (Schindler et al. 2021), cluster headache (Madsen et al. 2024) and more.

44 With such promising empirical data, research into elucidating mechanisms of action
45 becomes indispensable. It has long been known that the key receptor target for classical
46 serotonergic psychedelics is the 5HT_{2A} receptor (Nichols 2016), but that still tells us very little
47 about the complex effect these compounds clearly have on the human brain on all levels, from
48 deeper molecular mechanisms within cells to neuron-to-neuron interaction, regional activity
49 changes, whole-brain function changes all the way to subjective effects and observable behavior.
50 Fortunately, substantial progress is being made on all of these levels. Especially when looking at
51 their whole-brain and regional effects, it can be appreciated how psychedelics can also serve as a
52 tool for informing work in more theoretical areas of neuroscience such as consciousness research
53 (Rankaduwa and Owen 2023), painting a rich picture of the human brain function all the way from
54 health to disease and how that function can be externally perturbed and further studied that way.

55 Functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) allows for investigating multiple aspects
56 of brain function on this large-scale level, depending on the modality used. Task-based fMRI
57 studies visualize activations of brain areas in response to a defined stimulus (e.g. presentation of a
58 picture). On the other hand, resting-state fMRI studies investigate functional connectivity of brain
59 regions without any outside stimulus, thus reflecting (as the name suggests) communication
60 between brain areas at rest. This way, organization of the brain into so called canonical resting
61 state networks emerges. Functional connectivity can be further expanded upon in studies of
62 effective connectivity – this method employs further statistical methods to determine the direction
63 and valence (excitatory or inhibitory) of the signal (Chen and Glover 2015). A different approach
64 is presented by a heterogenous group of methods we collectively call here global measures, which
65 instead of subdividing the brain into areas study its functional integration as a whole.

66 There have been groundbreaking psychedelic fMRI studies made in the previous decades,
67 making findings that form the basis of current research and helping formulate the general
68 contemporary theories of psychedelic action on the brain – the most frequently discussed being
69 the Cortico-Striatal-Thalamo-Cortical (CSTC) model and the Relaxed Beliefs Under Psychedelics
70 (REBUS) model, as well as the more recent Cortico-Claustro-Cortical (CCC) model and a number
71 of others. More specifically, the CSTC model posits psychedelics to disinhibit the thalamus via
72 direct 5HT_{2A} receptor action, causing more excitatory action on the cortex, and thus weakening
73 its function as a filter and allowing more information to pass through – e.g. as visual hallucinations
74 (Vollenweider and Geyer 2001). The REBUS model builds on the predictive coding principle and

75 proposes that psychedelic drugs cause decrease in confidence in prior beliefs though increase in
76 brain entropy (see section 3.1 for definition and discussion of the term), and thus allow for their
77 revision (Carhart-Harris and Friston 2019). Other models have been proposed as well, such as the
78 CCC model, which attributes the observed desynchronization of canonical resting state networks
79 (such as the DMN) to their functional decoupling from the claustrum, which is rich in the 5HT2A
80 receptors (Doss et al. 2022). For a review of these models of psychedelic action, see (Doss et al.
81 2022).

82 As of now, as the field is further maturing, a sufficient number of papers exists to allow for
83 formulation of broader conceptual ‘flows’ within the current discourse independently of the
84 theoretical models, offering a broad snapshot of the current state of knowledge. There has already
85 been a number of review and systematic review articles conducted in this field, bringing into focus
86 various aspects of the developing field: a review (McCulloch et al. 2022b) and a systematic review
87 (Linguiti et al. 2023) of psychedelic neuroimaging mainly focused on methodology, a systematic
88 review specifically on the DMN modulation (Gattuso et al. 2022), a meta-analysis of functional
89 imaging (Castelhana et al. 2021), a review of neuroimaging in psilocybin-based psychotherapy
90 (Gill et al. 2022), and more (Muller and Borgwardt 2019, Soares 2023). Also see (Vollenweider
91 and Preller 2020) and (Kwan et al. 2022) for broader reviews of psychedelic mechanisms of action.
92 However, to the best of our knowledge, a work solely focused at summarising all of the current
93 themes within the findings in psychedelic fMRI has been missing. To remediate this gap, we have
94 conducted the present scoping review, which we believe would be valuable especially for new
95 researchers seeking to enter the field. We would also like to bring attention to a very recent review
96 published that brings valuable perspective on differences between fMRI (and PET) findings
97 between individual psychedelic substances (Frautschi et al. 2024), whereas we choose to treat the
98 serotonergic psychedelics as a whole.

99 For the sake of intelligibility, we cluster the results to several categories. There are multiple
100 possible ways to do this: by specific substances, by acute vs. longitudinal effects, by population
101 and more. We chose a rough clustering by different fMRI techniques as outlined above - each of
102 them examines different aspects of brain function not available to the others, thus reflecting distinct
103 processes (the line between these clusters naturally becoming blurry in multiple instances). In
104 addition, we add a specific section dedicated to ego dissolution, which seems to be emerging as a
105 key subjective phenomenon within the psychedelic experience, and which on its own carries
106 enough fMRI correlates to be discussed here separately. The findings we discuss in the narrative
107 text are those that have been detected by multiple studies, or are otherwise in line with other
108 research.

109

110 **2 Methods**

111 To conduct this scoping review, we carried out search of the existing literature on fMRI
112 imaging of the effect of serotonergic psychedelics, published as of time of search. Inclusion criteria
113 were: articles in English language, use of fMRI, direct analysis of fMRI data from human subjects
114 who received psilocybin, LSD, DMT, ayahuasca or mescaline. The literature available on Pubmed
115 was searched in September 2024. The following search string was applied: (*psychedelic OR*
116 *psilocybin OR lsd OR mescaline OR ayahuasca OR dimethyltryptamine*) *AND (fmri OR*

117 "functional magnetic" OR BOLD OR "arterial spin labeling") In total, 566 references were
118 obtained. See **Figure 1** for PRISMA flow diagram of study selection and for exclusion criteria.
119 Articles selected for analysis were extracted and organized using a reference manager, read in full
120 text and reviewed by M.B. and J.H. with disagreements resolved by discussion, and with all authors
121 then contributing to the information synthesis.

122 **3 Results**

123 A total of 71 original studies were reviewed in full text. 35 of these studies examined
124 psilocybin, 30 LSD, 8 ayahuasca and 5 DMT. There was no fMRI study concerning mescaline. As
125 for clustering by fMRI techniques we use in this review, 27 studies examined functional
126 connectivity, 22 global measures, 15 were task-based, and 7 examined effective connectivity.
127 Multiple studies examined more than one substance, and some studies belong into more than one
128 fMRI modality. Overview of findings from all studies reviewed is presented in **Table 1**. As
129 mentioned above, not all of these studies are discussed in the narrative text, as our main focus was
130 to capture broader concepts. Vast majority of studies examined the acute effect of the substances,
131 i.e. fMRI scans being acquired during intoxication; for studies where this is not the case (e.g. scans
132 made before and after intoxication), this fact is highlighted in **Table 1**. Methodological parameters
133 of all studies reviewed are presented in **Table 2**.

134 While the studies within the field remain very heterogenous, owing in part to the breadth
135 of problems possible to study *through* psychedelics, we have indeed been able to identify several
136 main themes which repeat in variations across studies and sometimes different substances. Some
137 of these have already been so widely replicated that they have their firm place in the current
138 discourse (e.g. decrease in modularity, increase in global connectivity), some correspond to the
139 respective models of psychedelic action described above, while others could be described as more
140 outlying.

141 **3.1 Global measures**

142 We begin with description of the effects psychedelics exert on the brain as a whole. Among
143 these, the clearest finding is a general increase in global functional connectivity, found across
144 multiple psychedelic substances (Timmermann et al. 2023, Tagliazucchi et al. 2016); in some
145 cases, the findings become more nuanced, observing a simultaneous increase in sensory global
146 connectivity and decrease in associative global connectivity (Preller et al. 2018b, 2020). Global
147 brain hyperconnection was also linked to heightened subjective effects (Mortaheb et al. 2024).

148 Another widely discussed finding is an increase in entropy, with one study even finding a
149 correlation with an increase in openness after 2 weeks (Lebedev et al. 2016). Entropy is a quantity
150 originally derived from thermodynamics, broadly defined as a measure of uncertainty of a system,
151 or the degree of its disorder – in neurobiological sense, this degree of disorder has been posited to
152 reflect the measure of subjective uncertainty and ultimately level of consciousness (Carhart-Harris
153 et al. 2014). It can also be viewed as a measure of complexity (Mikoláš et al. 2012). However,
154 entropy remains an elusive metric, with a number of different techniques employed to determine
155 it (see (McCulloch et al. 2024) for their discussion and evaluation). These include Shannon entropy
156 (Viol et al. 2017), sample entropy (Lebedev et al. 2016), entropy of possible states (Tagliazucchi
157 et al. 2014) or examining complexity more generally through brain activity fractal dimension

158 analysis (Varley et al. 2020). In addition, entropy is explored in EEG and MEG studies (Schartner
159 et al. 2017) – these however are beyond the scope of this paper.

160 Apart from these findings, there is a number of other experimental approaches to
161 examining global brain function, such as studies on brain dynamics, which investigate temporal
162 changes within the fMRI time series. Consistent with the findings of increased entropy, a series of
163 studies with psilocybin, LSD (Singleton et al. 2022) and DMT (Singleton et al. 2023) utilizing
164 network control theory has found a reduction of energy needed for transitioning from one brain
165 state (here defined as commonly recurring patterns of co-activation) to another, thus allowing for
166 more facile switching between them. Leading Eigenvector Dynamics Analysis (LEiDA), a method
167 examining time-varying functional connectivity patterns, has revealed a suppression of a pattern
168 corresponding to the fronto-parietal network and at the same time a state of increased global
169 coherence, suggestive of weakening of the normally present network structure and instead
170 transition into globally highly integrated state (Lord et al. 2019); a more recent study then
171 replicated these findings and found their correlation with psilocin plasma levels and subjective
172 drug effects (Olsen et al. 2022). General de-differentiation (we define de-differentiation here as a
173 reduction in normally present difference in function of distinct brain regions or networks) of brain
174 function was shown by a finding of a compression of a gradient of cortical hierarchy across
175 different psychedelic substances (Girn et al. 2022, Timmermann et al. 2023). Multiple studies have
176 also explored connectome harmonics in different substances, decomposing brain activity into
177 harmonic states to explore the functional connectome, and finding a move towards higher
178 frequencies representing a divergence from structural connectome – those findings can be
179 interpreted as a move towards criticality (Atasoy et al. 2017, Atasoy et al. 2018). The most recent
180 study in this area conducted with DMT also found correlation of these effects with subjective
181 intensity of the experience (Vohryzek et al. 2024).

182 In sum, these heterogenous studies show functional de-differentiation of the brain with
183 increased entropy and more fluid dynamics. These results can be interpreted as consistent with the
184 REBUS hypothesis, which posits a highly malleable state of the brain during the psychedelic
185 experience. Further work is now needed in reducing this heterogeneity (e.g. through replication)
186 to bring about a more coherent and rigorous basis for the REBUS model (McCulloch et al. 2024).

187 **3.2 Resting-state functional connectivity**

188 As described above, the brain is ordered into a number of resting-state networks under
189 normal circumstances. Among major of these, the central executive network (CEN) is associated
190 with focused attention, in contrast to the default mode network being associated with introspection;
191 the activity of these two networks is thus anticorrelated, with the salience network posited to switch
192 between them (Nekovarova et al. 2014). Possibly the most consistent finding within the fMRI of
193 the psychedelic state is a general dissolving of this brain modularity – a decrease in connectivity
194 within the resting-state networks, and increase in connectivity between them. This has been widely
195 replicated across different studies and different substances (Muller et al. 2018, Madsen et al. 2021,
196 Timmermann et al. 2023, Roseman et al. 2014). In line with these findings, network integrity has
197 been observed to negatively correlate with psilocin plasma levels and its subjective effects
198 (Madsen et al. 2021). Significantly, in a set of patients with treatment-resistant depression where
199 psilocybin was effective in treating their symptoms, this alleviation correlated with the decrease
200 in network modularity after dosing (Daws et al. 2022).

201 This modularity decrease seems to be the most pronounced in the DMN: its disintegration
202 correlates with subjective measures of ego-dissolution and with an improvement in psychosocial
203 functioning (Smigielski et al. 2019). In a study with ayahuasca, the decrease of connectivity within
204 the DMN lingered even 24 hours after dosing (Pasquini et al. 2020). In line with the general
205 breakdown of standard DMN functioning, there is a decrease of its anticorrelation with the task-
206 positive networks, normally a defining feature of the DMN (Carhart-Harris et al. 2013); a reduction
207 of functional connectivity between its components was one of the very first findings within the
208 psilocybin fMRI studies (Carhart-Harris et al. 2012a). Underscoring the importance of the DMN,
209 a recent longitudinal study found a decrease of its connectivity with anterior hippocampus, another
210 key structure implicated in the psychedelic state discussed below, lasting for 3 weeks after dosing
211 (Siegel et al. 2024).

212 A second major finding that has been widely replicated and discussed is an increase in
213 connectivity between the thalamus and the cortex (Müller et al. 2018, Tagliazucchi et al. 2016,
214 Preller et al. 2018b)(see also the general CSTC model – Vollenweider et al. 2001, Avram et al.
215 2021), with individual studies finding associations with subjective sensory effects (Avram et al.
216 2022, Müller et al. 2017). However, this connectivity pattern seems to be more complicated with
217 a closer look: more detailed analyses of thalamic connectivity bring conflicting and more nuanced
218 results. While one study with LSD found increased connectivity of the pulvinar and ventral nuclei
219 of thalamus with the cortex (Delli Pizzi et al. 2023b), a 7 tesla MRI study pinpointing the effect of
220 psilocybin on the thalamus to the pulvinar and the mediodorsal nucleus surprisingly found a
221 *decrease* in connectivity of these structures with cortical areas – consistent with these nuclei
222 maximally expressing the 5HT2A receptor within the thalamus (Gaddis et al. 2022).

223 Among other specific brain structures, there are numerous changes in the medial temporal
224 lobe structures, with a reduction of connectivity of the parahippocampal cortex correlating with
225 ego dissolution (Carhart-Harris et al. 2016), an already mentioned longitudinal decrease in
226 connectivity of the hippocampi with the DMN (Siegel et al. 2024) and an increase of signal
227 variability and entropy within them (Tagliazucchi et al. 2014); all of these studies being done with
228 psilocybin, while an infusion of DMT produced a deactivation of the hippocampi, which correlated
229 with subjective meaningfulness of the experience (Pasquini et al. 2024). Apart from the
230 hippocampus, the claustrum has been implicated in psychedelic drug action, with alterations of its
231 connectivity to the DMN, frontoparietal and auditory networks (Barrett et al. 2020b), forming the
232 basis of the CCC model (Doss et al. 2022); these findings have recently been corroborated by a
233 nonhuman primate study which found psilocybin-induced increase in connectivity of the claustrum
234 with the anterior cingulate cortex, the precuneus and areas of the prefrontal cortex (Bagdasarian et
235 al. 2024).

236 Taken together, studies on functional connectivity broadly show dissolving of resting-state
237 networks most prominent in the DMN, increase of thalamocortical connectivity with a need for
238 further clarification, decreases in connectivity of medial temporal lobe structures and alterations
239 of connectivity of the claustrum. The CCC model, while intriguing, is currently still based on only
240 one human study, making replication indispensable to prove its validity – the increasing use of
241 higher-resolution MRI scanners (see **Table 2**) has the potential to make studying this difficult-to-
242 measure structure more accessible.

243 **3.3 Task-based fMRI - activation studies**

244 A large number of activation studies have been conducted as well, with intriguing but
245 highly heterogenous paradigms and results, making any attempt at generalization difficult. A
246 closely examined brain region is the amygdala, a key structure of emotional processing that in
247 depression has been demonstrated to be hyperactive in response to negative stimuli and hypoactive
248 in response to positive stimuli (Stuhrmann et al. 2011), with this finding being attenuated by SSRI
249 treatment (Ma 2015). With psychedelics, multiple studies with psilocybin, LSD and ayahuasca
250 observe a decrease of its activity in response to negative stimuli (Barrett et al. 2020a, Kraehenmann
251 et al. 2015b, Arruda Sanchez et al. 2024); in one study, this correlated with the intensity of the
252 subjective effects (Mueller et al. 2017). A study of patients with treatment-resistant depression
253 found an increase of amygdala reactivity to both fearful and happy faces (in contrast to neutral
254 faces), with this phenomenon predictive of alleviation of depression in the first week after dosing
255 (Roseman et al. 2018). Thus, these findings seem to validate the potential of psychedelics to treat
256 depression, with an interesting difference of the finding of *increased* reactivity to happy *and* fearful
257 faces in the population of patients with depression. Additionally, changes to effective connectivity
258 of the amygdala have been identified by two studies discussed in the following section.

259 **3.4 Effective connectivity**

260 Findings of functional connectivity changes described above can be further expanded by
261 exploring effective connectivity (EC). Building on the CSTC model, LSD has been found to
262 increase EC from the thalamus to posterior cingulate cortex (a part of the DMN) while also
263 decreasing EC from striatum ventrale to the thalamus (Preller et al. 2019); it was also shown to
264 increase EC from the thalamus to both unimodal and transmodal cortex, contrasted to MDMA and
265 amphetamine which increased EC only to the unimodal cortex, highlighting a possible breach in
266 cortical hierarchy (see the section on global measures) as a feature unique to psychedelics (Avram
267 et al. 2023). Expanding on the picture of complex interplay between the main resting-state
268 networks with the central role of the DMN, LSD was shown to flip the valence of connectivity
269 (inhibitory to excitatory) from the salience network to the DMN, and decrease the inhibitory
270 connectivity from the DMN to the dorsal attention network (Stoliker et al. 2023). Lastly, the
271 knowledge on changes to amygdala was expanded by two studies: a) psilocybin was shown to
272 weaken modulatory effect of visual threat on the connection from the amygdala to primary visual
273 cortex (Kraehenmann et al. 2015a) and b) psilocybin decreased EC from cortical regions to the
274 amygdala, with the notable exception of the DMN (as well as to alter EC within the DMN, CEN
275 and SN), suggesting changes to hierarchical organization of brain function (Stoliker et al. 2024).
276 See **Figure 2** for schematic summary of effective connectivity changes.

277 Together with functional connectivity investigations, effective connectivity studies put the
278 CSTC model on a solid footing, showing the actual flow of information in the expected direction
279 and highlighting its breadth compared to non-psychedelic drugs. Regarding the model in general,
280 clarifications are needed as to precisely which cortical regions are affected; an attempt at
281 replicating the (Gaddis et al. 2022) study is warranted, as its findings challenge the model in its
282 current form.

283 **3.5 fMRI correlates of ego dissolution**

284 Lastly, outside importance of ego dissolution, a specific phenomenon within the
285 psychedelic experience characterised by a breakdown of the sense of self (Stoliker et al. 2022), is

286 becoming clear through fMRI studies. In itself, ego dissolution is not an fMRI concept, but a
287 subjective phenomenon – in psychedelic research these are generally ascertained by psychometric
288 scales, such as the Five Dimensional Altered States Of Consciousness (5D-ASC). This scale
289 groups the subjective elements of the psychedelic experience into 3 main themes (Visionary
290 Restructuralization, Oceanic Boundlessness and Anxious-Ego Dissolution) with 11 subthemes
291 among these. We choose to include ego dissolution as a section here as there are multiple fMRI
292 findings associated specifically with it, and it has connections beyond them, with its extent shown
293 to predict positive changes in psycho-social functioning 4 months after dosing of psilocybin
294 (Smigielski et al. 2019). In relation to fMRI, its occurrence is specifically associated with a
295 decrease in connectivity between the parahippocampal cortex and retrosplenial cortex (Carhart-
296 Harris et al. 2016), decrease in connectivity between the medial temporal lobe and the cortex,
297 disintegration of the salience network and a decrease in interhemispheric communication (Lebedev
298 et al. 2015). The changes observed by (Stoliker et al. 2023) described in the section on effective
299 connectivity also correlated with measures of ego dissolution. In addition, an increase in global
300 connectivity (Tagliazucchi et al. 2016) and disintegration of the DMN (Smigielski et al. 2019)
301 have been observed specifically during ego dissolution, both in line with more general findings
302 during the psychedelic experience, suggesting their deepening during this phenomenon. However,
303 as stated above, fMRI correlates are just one of many aspects of ego dissolution - for a
304 comprehensive review of its mechanisms, see (Stoliker et al. 2022).

305 **4 Discussion**

306 Taken together, a look at the entirety of the studies reviewed offers a rich and diverse
307 landscape of findings, where lines of consistency are starting to take shape. These lines are present
308 both ‘horizontally’ in the form of converging results we have highlighted here, but also ‘vertically’,
309 in the form of associations with findings outside of the fMRI sphere: namely with the subjectively
310 reported effects, drug plasma levels, and also different neuroimaging modalities (e.g. employment
311 of simultaneously recorded EEG-fMRI (Timmermann et al. 2023)). Overall, this consistency is
312 putting the fMRI findings on firmer footing. Another instance of this could be seen in tracking of
313 longitudinal changes, with well-known studies that show persisting effects through subjective
314 measures (Griffiths et al. 2018) and through disease symptom remission (Carhart-Harris et al.
315 2021) recently being shored up by findings of fMRI changes persisting as well (Siegel et al. 2024,
316 Pasquini et al. 2020, McCulloch et al. 2022a, Barrett et al. 2020a). Given the time course of mental
317 disorders potentially treatable by psychedelics, possibility of their relapse and discussions of
318 deeper personality change through psychedelic treatment, further ascertaining the specifics of
319 these long-term effects will be a crucial direction moving forward.

320 Further research into subdivision of the psychedelic state itself also appears crucial - this
321 is exemplified by studies on ego dissolution, which generally show specific changes unique to this
322 phenomenon and not present in the psychedelic state as a whole, and which have been shown to
323 translate into long-term effects (Smigielski et al. 2019), demonstrating their significance. An
324 example of advancing this line of thinking can be seen in recent studies on DMT (Timmermann et
325 al. 2023), which take advantage of its short half-life allowing to capture the whole or most of the
326 psychedelic state within the session.

327 With progress in the MR technology itself, findings suggestive a new level of complexity
328 are emerging and showing the necessity of further clarification to established findings, such as the

329 discovery of decreased thalamocortical connectivity when looking at individual thalamic nuclei
330 by (Gaddis et al. 2022). Further, as new approaches are also being developed in the area of global
331 measures, the overarching picture of general de-differentiation of brain function keeps emerging
332 through a wide variety of different techniques - this would seem to be broadly consistent with the
333 REBUS hypothesis, and speculatively with the potential of psychedelics being able to act
334 transdiagnostically (Kočárová et al. 2021, Carhart-Harris et al. 2023). Further work on integrating
335 the models of action together is warranted.

336 Lastly, a meaningful route of filtering out noise and exploring neurobiological
337 undercurrents appears to be one of drawing contrasts between psychedelics and
338 phenomenologically similar yet neurobiologically different states: a) those elicited by
339 psychoactive substances other than classical psychedelics, such as the finding that MDMA (and
340 amphetamine) increase effective connectivity to unimodal cortex contrasted with LSD increasing
341 EC also to transmodal cortex (Avram et al. 2023), of methylphenidate (which was used in the study
342 as an active control) showing changes corresponding to general arousal contrasted with more
343 specific changes of psilocybin (Siegel et al. 2024), or of ketamine (and NO) producing similar
344 changes (decrease in within-network connectivity and increase in between-network connectivity)
345 to LSD (Dai et al. 2023); and b) altered states of consciousness such as meditation, hypnosis or
346 schizophrenia. Specifically, the parallels with schizophrenia form an avenue of research as old as
347 the psychedelic substances themselves (Nichols 2016), which is promising inways into two states
348 that both warrant more complete understanding, as well as into more fundamental concepts of
349 neuroscience and psychology such as the self, of which there are clear alterations in both conditions
350 (Kozáková et al. 2020, Stoliker et al. 2022). There has been a constant stream of studies drawing
351 these parallels with schizophrenia, many of which are consistent with the themes explored in this
352 review: altered thalamocortical connectivity (Avram et al. 2021), disruption to the DMN-task
353 positive network anticorrelation (Carhart-Harris et al. 2013), principal cortical gradient
354 compression (Girn et al. 2022, Timmermann et al. 2023). Another compelling parallel could be
355 represented by the deep disruptions within the triad of DMN, central executive and salience
356 network, which have also been described in schizophrenia (Nekovarova et al. 2014). For further
357 discussions on this topic, see also (Leptourgos et al. 2020, Sapienza et al. 2023). As for meditation,
358 previous studies have intriguingly shown changes in similar areas compared to psychedelics, such
359 as more robust DMN activation compared to rest (Xu et al. 2014) and subacute increase in
360 connectivity of the DMN with the dorsal attention network and visual cortex (Zhang et al. 2021);
361 see (Boccia et al. 2015) for a meta-analysis. For a direct comparison of fMRI correlates of the
362 psychedelic state, hypnosis and meditation, see (Moujaes et al. 2024).

363 From a methodological standpoint and as highlighted by (McCulloch et al. 2022b), there
364 is a great need for more independent replication of the available findings, as the studies available
365 come from a limited number of relatively small datasets. To this end, focus on data standardization
366 will be crucial moving forward, as currently there is a great degree of heterogeneity in multiple
367 aspects. Scan timepoints vary, and while each of them may be justified (or simply necessary, e.g.
368 with the need to fit multiple tasks into one administration session), the resulting data originate
369 from different sections of the psychedelic experience – this can be a complication for instance in
370 studying ego dissolution, as it is a phenomenon that occurs only during a fraction of the whole
371 experience. Further complicating matters, drug administration methods vary, with both per os and
372 i.v. being utilised, resulting in different plasma level dynamics for some substances and thus
373 making it difficult to pinpoint equivalent scan timepoints. Another potential source of

374 heterogeneity lies in fMRI data processing, for instance in using in-house pre-processing pipelines,
375 which by definition vary between institutions, and can for example influence whether a given result
376 reaches the level of statistical significance or not. Finally, subject characteristics can be a source
377 of heterogeneity - in a large part of the ayahuasca studies, participants were experienced users,
378 while long term use of ayahuasca has been shown to elicit structural changes (specifically, thinning
379 of the posterior cingulate cortex) in the brain (Bouso et al. 2015), potentially leading to different
380 fMRI findings compared to first-time users; other example would be potential differences between
381 clinical populations and healthy volunteers. In sum, this heterogeneity will need to be taken into
382 account in studies aiming to replicate these results.

383 **5 Limitations**

384 There are limitations to this study to be mentioned here. While our aim was to offer a
385 conceptual overview of the field, this led to a large number of existing studies not being mentioned
386 in the narrative text for the sake of clarity. Furthermore, with the decision to mostly treat the
387 serotonergic psychedelics as a whole also necessary to formulate a somewhat digestible picture of
388 the field, it is naturally an oversimplification, with significant differences among the substances in
389 themselves. Perhaps the most obvious of these would be different pharmacokinetics, for instance
390 half-life (approximately 4 hours for LSD, compared to only 5-15 minutes for DMT), but also speed
391 of onset and offset, adding to the heterogeneity discussed above (Holze et al. 2024). Differences
392 also lie in subjective effects, in the simplest form in perceived intensity of the experience, but also
393 in more nuanced phenomenological aspects – for instance in the form of perceived entity
394 encounters, which is a phenomenon characteristic for DMT. There are also nuances in receptor
395 profiles of the substances. Generally, these differences could be explored by further research
396 combining fMRI with other modalities: namely, studies with PET (both FDG and specific receptor
397 ligands) and EEG. Also refer to (Frautschi et al. 2024) for a discussion of this heterogeneity.

398 As for methodological limitations, only one database (PubMed) was used to search for
399 articles – however, given that it is a database most relevant in the research field (neuroscience with
400 overlap into psychiatry) and we did not aim to review entries such as conference abstracts or case
401 reports, we do not consider this a major limitation. Risk of bias assessment and review protocol
402 pre-registration were not performed for this scoping review.

403 **6 Conclusion**

404 In conclusion, we show that numerous changes to brain function induced by serotonergic
405 psychedelics have been observed using fMRI. The converging findings with the strongest evidence
406 are: a general increase in connectivity throughout the brain, increase in entropy, dissolution of
407 resting-state brain networks which is most pronounced in the DMN, increased thalamocortical
408 connectivity, decreased amygdala reactivity to negative stimuli, changes to medial temporal lobe
409 structures, and the significance of ego dissolution. In addition, a diverse array of other individual
410 results show possible directions of further research. Independent replication of these findings and
411 their further validation through associations with drug plasma levels, subjective and longitudinal
412 effects, as well as with findings from other imaging modalities, will be necessary moving forward.

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422 **8 Declaration of interest statement**

423 T.P. and J.H. founded the PSYRES-Psychedelic Research Foundation and have shares in
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425 from GH Research and CB21-Pharma outside the submitted work and is involved in Compass
426 Pathways and/or MAPS clinical trial with psilocybin/MDMA trials outside the submitted work.
427 The remaining authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial
428 or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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Table 1: Summary of findings of and techniques utilised in the reviewed studies

775 ACC anterior cingulate cortex, BOLD blood-oxygen-level-dependent imaging, CBF cerebral blood flow, CEN central executive
 776 network, DAN dorsal attention network, DMN default mode network, dmPFC dorsomedial prefrontal cortex, EC effective
 777 connectivity, FC functional connectivity, LFF low frequency fluctuations, mOFC medial orbitofrontal cortex, mPFC medial
 778 prefrontal cortex, MTL medial temporal lobe, PCC posterior cingulate cortex, PFC prefrontal cortex, PHC parahippocampal
 779 cortex, SN salience network, vmPFC ventromedial prefrontal cortex

<u>Authors</u>	<u>Substance</u>	<u>Method details</u>	<u>Main finding</u>
<u>Global Measures</u>			
Tagliazucchi et al. 2014	Psilocybin 2 mg i.v.	Dynamic rsFC	Increased time variability and entropy in hippocampi and ACC; increased number of connectivity motifs
Lord et al. 2019	Psilocybin 2 mg i.v.	Leading Eigenvector Dynamics Analysis (LEiDA)	Destabilization of frontoparietal subsystem and instead increase in global coherence
Preller et al. 2020	Psilocybin 14mg/70kg p.o.	Global brain connectivity	Increased sensory global connectivity and decreased associative global connectivity; baseline connectivity associated with magnitude of changes
Olsen et al. 2022	Psilocybin 0.24±0.04 mg/kg	Leading Eigenvector Dynamics Analysis (LEiDA)	Negative correlation of frontoparietal state occurrence with psilocin plasma levels and subjective drug effects, positive correlation of global brain state with psilocin plasma levels and subjective drug effects
Daws et al. 2022	Psilocybin 10mg and 25mg p.o. (open label); Psilocybin 2x 25 mg p.o. (DB-RCT)	Brain network modularity; measured after intoxication	Brain network modularity was decreased 1 day after treatment, which correlated with alleviation of depressive symptoms after 6 months
Morthaheb et al. 2024	Psilocybin 0,17mg/kg	Time-varying functional connectivity analysis	Increased averaged brain functional connectivity, hyperconnected pattern with low BOLD signal amplitude, correlation with feelings of oceanic boundlessness and visionary restructuralization
Varley et al. 2020	LSD 75µg i.v., psilocybin 2mg i.v.	Fractal dimension of functional connectivity	Increased fractal dimension of networks and BOLD signal, suggestive of increased entropy, localized to dorsal attention network
Girn et al. 2022	LSD 75µg i.v., psilocybin 2mg i.v.	Gradient-mapping analysis	Flattening of principal gradient of cortical connectivity
Singleton et al. 2022	LSD 75µg i.v., psilocybin 2mg i.v.	Network control analysis	Reduction of control energy needed for transitioning between brain states
Luppi et al. 2023	LSD 75µg i.v., psilocybin 2mg i.v., DMT 20mg i.v., ayahuasca (2.2 ml/kg containing 0.8 mg/ml of DMT and 0.21 mg/ml of harmine) (10 substances in total)	Effects of different substances and cortical distributions of neurotransmitters on FC	Effects of compared substances organized along the principal cortical gradient

<u>Authors</u>	<u>Substance</u>	<u>Method details</u>	<u>Main finding</u>
Tagliazucchi et al. 2016	LSD 75µg i.v.	Global functional connectivity	Increase in global integration by increase in connectivity between normally distinct networks, correlating with ego dissolution
Lebedev et al. 2016	LSD 75µg i.v.	Sample entropy	Increased entropy, which predicted increased openness after two weeks
Atasoy et al. 2017	LSD 75µg i.v.	Connectome-harmonic decomposition	Expansion of the repertoire of active brain states, move towards criticality
Preller et al. 2018b	LSD 100µg p.o.	Global brain connectivity	Increased sensory-somatomotor whole-brain and thalamic connectivity, decreased associative connectivity
Luppi et al. 2021	LSD 75µg i.v.	Dynamic rsFC	Weakening of the relationship between functional and anatomic connectivity; ego-dissolution predicted by increase in small-world organization; also decrease of FC of mPFC
Lawn et al. 2022	LSD 75µg i.v.	Receptor-enriched analysis of functional connectivity by targets	Serotonergic system is associated with perception changes, dopaminergic system with perceived selfhood and cognition
Viol et al. 2017	Ayahuasca (2.2 ml/kg containing 0.8 mg/ml of DMT and 0.21 mg/ml of harmine)	Shannon entropy	Increase in entropy and local network integration, decrease in global integration
Mallaroni et al. 2024	Ayahuasca (mean 24ml, containing 0.14 mg/ml of DMT, 4.50 mg/ml of harmine, 0.51 mg/ml of harmaline, and 2.10 mg/ml of tetrahydroharmine)	Static and dynamic functional connectivity	Interindividual differences in higher functional connectivity motifs predict perceptual effects
Timmermann et al. 2023	DMT 20mg i.v.	Global functional connectivity	Increase in global functional connectivity, disintegration and desegregation of networks, compression of principal cortical gradient
Singleton et al. 2023	DMT 20mg i.v.	Network control analysis	Reduction of control energy needed for transitioning between brain states
Pasquini et al. 2024	DMT 20mg i.v.	Dynamic activity matrix	Increased superior temporal lobe activity; Decreased hippocampal and medial parietal cortex activity, which correlated with meaningfulness of the experience
Vohryzek et al. 2024	DMT 7/14/18/20mg i.v.	Connectome-harmonic decomposition	Move towards higher frequencies, divergence from structural connectome, move towards criticality
<u>Resting-state functional connectivity</u>			
Carhart-Harris et al. 2012a	Psilocybin 2 mg i.v.		Decreased CBF and BOLD especially in thalamus, ACC and PCC; decreased connectivity between mPFC and PCC

<u>Authors</u>	<u>Substance</u>	<u>Method details</u>	<u>Main finding</u>
Carhart-Harris et al. 2013	Psilocybin 2 mg i.v.		Decrease in anticorrelation of the DMN and task-positive network (increase in FC between them)
Roseman et al. 2014	Psilocybin 2 mg i.v. (MDMA)		Increased between-network connectivity
Lebedev et al. 2015	Psilocybin 2 mg i.v.		Measures of ego-dissolution correlated with decreased FC between MTL and the cortex, with disintegration of the salience network and with decreased interhemispheric communication
Carhart-Harris et al. 2017	Psilocybin 10mg and 25mg p.o.	Measured intoxication after	Increase in FC within DMN post-treatment in treatment-resistant depression
Smigielski et al. 2019	Psilocybin 315 µg/kg p.o.		Decreased FC between mPFC and PCC, associated with ego-dissolution, which predicted positive changes in psychosocial functioning after 4 months
Barrett et al. 2020a	Psilocybin 25mg/70kg p.o.	Measured intoxication after	Increase in significant connections after 1 week and 1 month
Barrett et al. 2020b	Psilocybin 10mg/70kg p.o.		Decreased BOLD variance and LFF amplitude in the claustra, predicted by subjective effects; various changes in their network connectivity
Madsen et al. 2021	Psilocybin 0,2-0,3mg/kg p.o.		Psilocin plasma levels and subjective effects negatively correlate with network integrity, positively with CEN and DAN desegregation and connectivity to rest of the brain
Gaddis et al. 2022	Psilocybin 10mg/70kg p.o.		Decreased FC between mediodorsal nucleus of the thalamus and the pulvinar with the DMN and visual network; magnitude of these changes correlated with subjective effects
McCulloch et al. 2022a	Psilocybin 0,2-0,3mg/kg p.o.	Measured intoxication after	Decrease of CEN FC after 1 week, this predicted increase in mindfulness after 3 months
Madsen et al. 2024	Psilocybin 0,14mg/kg 3 times	Measured intoxication after	Negative correlation of hypothalamic-diencephalic FC and percent change in chronic cluster headache attack frequency
Siegel et al. 2024	Psilocybin 25mg p.o. (Methylphenidate)	Longitudinal rsFC tracking; measured also after intoxication	Reduced correlations within and anticorrelations between networks, most pronounced in the DMN; decrease in FC between DMN and the hippocampus lasting weeks
Moujaes et al. 2023	LSD 100µg p.o., psilocybin 0.2mg/kg p.o.		Psilocybin and LSD effect determined by machine learning differed from hypnosis and meditation
Carhart-Harris et al. 2016	LSD 75µg i.v.		Decreased FC between PHC and retrosplenial cortex correlated with ratings of ego-dissolution and altered meaning

<u>Authors</u>	<u>Substance</u>	<u>Method details</u>	<u>Main finding</u>
Tagliazucchi et al. 2016	LSD 75µg i.v.		Increased FC between association cortex and the thalamus; increase in global FC correlating with measures of ego-dissolution
Speth et al. 2016	LSD 75µg i.v.		Decreased FC within the DMN, which correlated with decrease of language references to the past
Müller et al. 2017	LSD 100µg p.o.		Increased FC between thalamus and cortical areas; the increase in FC specifically with fusiform gyrus and insula correlated with subjective auditory and visual effects
Müller et al. 2018	LSD 100µg p.o.		Decrease of FC within visual, sensorimotor, auditory and default-mode networks, and increase in FC within all networks and between networks and the thalamus, striatum, precuneus and ACC
Avram et al. 2022	LSD 100µg p.o.(MDMA, D-amphetamine)		Increased FC between thalamus and auditory, sensorimotor (all substances) and SN (LSD only)
Dai et al. 2023	LSD 75µg i.v. (NO, ketamine)		All 3 substances decreased within-network connectivity and increased between-network connectivity
Delli Pizzi et al. 2023a	LSD 75µg i.v.		Increase in FC and signal amplitude in default-mode and attention networks rich with 2A receptors; decrease of FC and signal amplitude in limbic areas rich in 1A receptors
Delli Pizzi et al. 2023b	LSD 75µg i.v.		Increased FC between thalamamic ventral nuclei, pulvinar and sensory and association cortex
Shukuroglou et al. 2023	Psilocybin 10mg and 25mg p.o.	Measured intoxication	after Decrease of FC between nucleus accumbens and the DMN after music listening during dosing for treatment-resistant depression, compared to dosing without music listening
Palhano-Fontes et al. 2015	Ayahuasca (2.2 ml/kg containing 0.8 mg/ml of DMT and 0.21 mg/ml of harmine)		Decrease of activity in the DMN and decrease of FC between PCC and precuneus
Sampedro et al. 2017	Ayahuasca (148±29ml, containing 0.36mg/ml DMT, 0.86mg/ml harmine, 0.17mg/ml tetrahydroharmine, and 0.04mg/ml harmaline)	Measured intoxication	after Postacute increase of ACC FC of PCC and right MTL; changes predicted with increase in nonjudging after 2 months
Pasquini et al. 2020	Ayahuasca (1ml/kg, containing 0.36mg/ml of N,N-DMT, 1.86mg/ml of harmine, 0.24mg/ml of harmaline, and 1.20mg/ml of tetrahydroharmine)	Measured intoxication	after Increase in FC of ACC within the salience network and decrease of FC of PCC within the DMN
<u>Effective connectivity</u>			

<u>Authors</u>	<u>Substance</u>	<u>Method details</u>	<u>Main finding</u>
Kraehenmann et al. 2015a	Psilocybin 0.16 mg/kg p.o.		Decrease by threat-induced connectivity from amygdala to V1 visual cortex
Stoliker et al. 2024	Psilocybin 0,2mg/kg p.o.		Decrease of EC from cortical regions to the amygdala, with the exception of the DMN
Kaelen et al. 2016	LSD 75µg i.v.		Increase of FC and EC from PHC to visual cortex during music listening
Preller et al. 2019	LSD 100µg p.o.		Increase of EC from thalamus to PCC and decrease of EC from striatum ventrale to the thalamus
Stoliker et al. 2023	LSD 100µg p.o.		Change of inhibitory EC from SN to DMN to excitatory and decrease of inhibitory EC from DMN to DAN during ego dissolution
Avram et al. 2023	LSD 100µg p.o. (MDMA, D-amphetamine)		Increase of EC from thalamus to unimodal cortex by all substances, LSD additionally increased EC from thalamus to transmodal cortex
Bedford et al. 2023	LSD 100µg p.o.	Regression DCM	Stronger FC and EC with the exception of connections involving occipital and subcortical regions; perturbed excitation/inhibition balance
<u>Task-based fMRI - activation studies</u>			
Carhart-Harris et al. 2012b	Psilocybin 2 mg i.v.		Activation in visual and other sensory areas while watching 15 positive autobiographical stimuli
Kraehenmann et al. 2015b	Psilocybin 0.16 mg/kg p.o.		Decreased amygdala reactivity to negative and neutral stimuli
Preller et al. 2016	Psilocybin 0.215mg/kg p.o.		Decreased response to social exclusion in dorsal ACC and the middle frontal gyrus
Roseman et al. 2018	Psilocybin 10mg and 25mg p.o.	Measured intoxication after	Increase of right amygdala reactivity to fearful and happy faces in treatment-resistant depression
Barrett et al. 2020a	Psilocybin 25mg/70kg p.o.	Measured intoxication after	Decreased amygdala activation in response to faces and increased DMPFC and mOFC in response to emotionally conflicting stimuli one week after dosing
Mertens et al. 2020	Psilocybin 10mg and 25mg p.o.	Measured intoxication after	Decreased connectivity of vmPFC with right amygdala during processing of fearful and neutral faces in treatment-resistant depression
Duerler et al. 2022	Psilocybin 0.2 mg/kg p.o.		Decrease in activity in frontal areas, visual cortex and cerebellum in response to tactile mismatch responses

<u>Authors</u>	<u>Substance</u>	<u>Method details</u>	<u>Main finding</u>
Pagni et al. 2024	Psilocybin 25mg/70 kg p.o.	Measured after intoxication	Increase of PFC and caudate and decrease in insula, motor cortex and cerebellum activity with visual and emotionally valenced stimuli in patients with alcohol use disorder
Mueller et al. 2017	LSD 100µg p.o.		Reduced amygdala and right mPFC reactivity to fearful faces
Preller et al. 2017	LSD 100µg p.o.		Induction of attribution of personal relevance to previously meaningless stimuli and modulated the processing of meaningful stimuli in dorsal ACC, PCC
Preller et al. 2018a	LSD 100µg p.o.		Reduction of activity in PCC and angular gyrus in social interaction task
Schmidt et al. 2018	LSD 100µg p.o.		In Go/No-Go Task, impaired inhibitory performance related to parahippocampal and left superior frontal gyrus activation
Duerler et al. 2020	LSD 100µg p.o.		Increased mPFC activity in social adaptation task
de Araujo et al. 2011	Ayahuasca (2.2 ml/kg containing 0.8 mg/ml of DMT and 0.21 mg/ml of harmine)		Activation in V1 visual cortex during closed eyes imagery task to same degree as with eyes open (lesse arctivations in occipital, temporal and frontal areas)
Arruda Sanchez et al. 2024	Ayahuasca (30ml/70kg, corresponding to 0.333mg/kg DMT, 0.473mg/kg Harmine, 0.023mg/kg Harmaline, and 0.470mg/kg THH)		Decreased amygdala activation with implicit aversive stimulation in face recognition task

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Table 2: Summary of methodologies of reviewed studies

<u>Authors</u>	<u>Substance</u>	<u>Comparator condition, study design</u>	<u>Sample details</u>	<u>Timing of scan</u>	<u>Scanner information</u>
<u>Global Measures</u>					
Tagliazucchi et al. 2014	Psilocybin 2 mg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects	15 healthy subjects, 13 males and 2 females, mean age = 32y	60 s infusion exactly 6 min after the start of the 12 min scan	3T GE HDx system
Lord et al. 2019	Psilocybin 2 mg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects	15 healthy subjects, 13 males and 2 females, mean age = 32y	60 s infusion exactly 6 min after the start of the 12 min scan	3T GE HDx system
Preller et al. 2020	Psilocybin 14mg/70kg p.o.	Placebo, double-blinded, randomized, crossover design	23 healthy subjects, 12 males, 11 females, mean age = 26.3y	20, 40, and 70 minutes after treatment administration	3T Philips Achieva
Olsen et al. 2022	Psilocybin 0.24±0.04 mg/kg	Ketanserin, crossover design	15 healthy subjects, 6 females, mean age 34.3y ± 9.8 years	Once before and approx. 40, 80, 130, and 300 min after administration	3T Siemens Prisma scanner
Daws et al. 2022	Psilocybin 10mg and 25mg p.o. (open label); Psilocybin 2x 25 mg p.o. (DB-RCT)	Baseline, open label trial and double-blind randomized controlled trial	16 subjects with TRD, 4 female, mean age = 42.75y, SD = 10.15 (open label); 22 subjects with TRD, 8 female, mean age = 44.5y, SD = 11.0 (DB-RCT))	At baseline and 1 day after second dosing (open label); At baseline and 3 weeks after second dosing (DB-RCT)	3T Siemens Tim Trio
Morthaheb et al. 2024	Psilocybin 0,17mg/kg	Placebo, randomized	49 healthy subjects (psilocybin n = 22, 12 male; mean age = 23y, SD = 2,9; placebo n = 27, 15 male, age = 23.1y, SD = 3.8)	Subjects placed in scanner 40 minutes after administration, scans performed throughout a 1-hour time window	7T Siemens MAGNETO M scanner
Varley et al. 2020	LSD 75µg i.v., psilocybin 2mg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects (both substances)	20 healthy subjects, 4 females, mean age = 30.9y±7.8 (LSD), 15 healthy subjects, 13 males and 2 females, mean age = 32y (psilocybin)	60 minutes after infusion (LSD), 60 s infusion exactly 6 min after the start of the 12 min scan (psilocybin)	3T GE HDx system
Girn et al. 2022	LSD 75µg i.v., psilocybin 2mg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects (both substances)	20 healthy subjects, 4 females, mean age = 30.9y±7.8 (LSD), 15 healthy subjects, 13 males and 2 females, mean age = 32y (psilocybin)	60 minutes after infusion (LSD), 60 s infusion exactly 6 min after the start of the 12 min scan (psilocybin)	3T GE HDx system
Singleton et al. 2022	LSD 75µg i.v., psilocybin 2mg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects (both substances)	20 healthy subjects, 4 females, mean age = 30.9y±7.8 (LSD), 15 healthy subjects, 13 males and 2 females, mean age = 32y (psilocybin)	60 minutes after infusion (LSD), 60 s infusion exactly 6 min after the start of the 12 min scan (psilocybin)	3T GE HDx system
Luppi et al. 2023	LSD 75µg i.v., psilocybin 2mg i.v., DMT 20mg i.v., ayahuasca (2.2 ml/kg containing 0.8 mg/ml of DMT and 0.21 mg/ml of harmine) (10 substances in total)	Placebo, within-subjects (LSD, psilocybin); Placebo, single-blind, counter-balanced (DMT); Baseline, open label (ayahuasca)	(Carhart-Harris et al. 2016) for LSD, (Carhart-Harris et al. 2012) for psilocybin, (Timmermann et al. 2023) for DMT, (Viol et al. 2017) for ayahuasca		

<u>Authors</u>	<u>Substance</u>	<u>Comparator condition, study design</u>	<u>Sample details</u>	<u>Timing of scan</u>	<u>Scanner information</u>
Tagliazucchi et al. 2016	LSD 75µg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects	20 healthy subjects, 4 females, mean age = 30.9y±7.8	60 minutes after infusion	3T GE HDx system
Lebedev et al. 2016	LSD 75µg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects	20 healthy subjects, 4 females, mean age = 30.9y±7.8	60 minutes after infusion	3T GE HDx system
Atasoy et al. 2017	LSD 75µg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects	20 healthy subjects, 4 females, mean age = 30.9y±7.8 (12 used)	60 minutes after infusion	3T GE HDx system
Preller et al. 2018b	LSD 100µg p.o.	Placebo/ketanserin, double-blind, randomized, crossover design	24 healthy subjects, 5 females, mean age = 25.00y; SD = 3,60	75 and 300 min after treatment administration	3T Philips Achieva
Luppi et al. 2021	LSD 75µg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects	20 healthy subjects, 4 females, mean age = 30.9y±7.8	60 minutes after infusion	3T GE HDx system
Lawn et al. 2022	LSD 75µg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects	15 healthy subjects, 11 females, mean age = 30.5y ± 8.0	60 minutes after infusion	3T GE HDx system
Viol et al. 2017	Ayahuasca (2.2 ml/kg containing 0.8 mg/ml of DMT and 0.21 mg/ml of harmine)	Baseline, open label	9 healthy subjects, 5 females	before and 40 minutes subsequent to Ayahuasca intake	1.5T Siemens Magnetom Vision
Mallaroni et al. 2024	Ayahuasca (mean 24ml, containing 0.14 mg/ml of DMT, 4.50 mg/ml of harmine, 0.51 mg/ml of harmaline, and 2.10 mg/ml of tetrahydroharmine)	Baseline, within-subject, fixed-order observational study	21 healthy subjects (experienced Santo Daime members), 10 females, mean age = 54.48y, SD = 10.55	1 hour after intake	7T Siemens MAGNETOM scanner
Timmermann et al. 2023	DMT 20mg i.v.	Placebo, single-blind, counter-balanced	20 healthy subjects, 7 female, mean age = 33.5y, SD = 7.9	Scans lasting 28 min with DMT/placebo administered at the end of 8th min and scanning being over 20 min after injection	3T Siemens Magnetom Verio syngo MR B17
Singleton et al. 2023	DMT 20mg i.v.	Placebo, single-blind, counter-balanced	20 healthy subjects, 7 female, mean age = 33.5y, SD = 7.9	Scans lasting 28 min with DMT/placebo administered at the end of 8th min and scanning being over 20 min after injection	3T Siemens Magnetom Verio syngo MR B17
Pasquini et al. 2024	DMT 20mg i.v.	Placebo, single-blind, counter-balanced	14 healthy subjects, 4 females, mean age = 34.1y, SD = 8.8	Scans lasting 28 min with DMT/placebo administered at the end of 8th min and scanning being over 20 min after injection	3T Siemens Magnetom Verio syngo MR B17
Vohryzek et al. 2024	DMT 7/14/18/20mg i.v.	Placebo, fixed-order, single-blind	20 healthy subjects, 7 females, mean age = 33.5y, SD = 7.9	DMT/placebo bolus in 8th minute of 28-minute scan	3T Siemens Magnetom Verio syngo MR 12
<u>Resting-state functional connectivity</u>					

<u>Authors</u>	<u>Substance</u>	<u>Comparator condition, study design</u>	<u>Sample details</u>	<u>Timing of scan</u>	<u>Scanner information</u>
Carhart-Harris et al. 2012a	Psilocybin 2 mg i.v.	Placebo, within-subject	15 healthy subjects, 13 males and 2 females, mean age = 32y	60 s infusion exactly 6 min after the start of the 12 min scan	3T GE HDx system
Carhart-Harris et al. 2013	Psilocybin 2 mg i.v.	Placebo, within-subject	15 healthy subjects, 13 males and 2 females, mean age = 32y	60 s infusion exactly 6 min after the start of the 12 min scan	3T GE HDx system
Roseman et al. 2014	Psilocybin 2 mg i.v. (MDMA)	Placebo, within-subject	15 healthy subjects, 13 males and 2 females, mean age = 32y	60 s infusion exactly 6 min after the start of the 12 min scan	3T GE HDx system
Lebedev et al. 2015	Psilocybin 2 mg i.v.	Placebo, within-subject	15 healthy subjects, 13 males and 2 females, mean age = 32y	60 s infusion exactly 6 min after the start of the 12 min scan	3T GE HDx system
Carhart-Harris et al. 2017	Psilocybin 10mg and 25mg p.o.	Baseline, open-label	16 subjects with TRD, 4 female, mean age = 42.75y, SD = 10.15	At baseline and 1 day after second dosing	3T Siemens Tim Trio
Smigielski et al. 2019	Psilocybin 315 µg/kg p.o.	Placebo, double-blind, randomized	38 healthy, experienced meditator subjects (20 in active group), 15 females, mean age = 51.66y, SD = 8.32	Day before and after a 5-day meditation retreat with psilocybin administered on fourth day	3T Philips Achieva
Barrett et al. 2020a	Psilocybin 25mg/70kg p.o.	Baseline, open-label	12 healthy subjects, 7 females, mean age = 32.1y, SD = 7.5	One day before, one week after, and one month after psilocybin administration	3T Philips Achieva
Barrett et al. 2020b	Psilocybin 10mg/70kg p.o.	Placebo, blinded	15 healthy subjects, 5 females, mean age = 51.3y, SD = 12.3	100 minutes after administration	3T Philips Achieva
Madsen et al. 2021	Psilocybin 0,2-0,3mg/kg p.o.	Non-psychedelic drug, blinded	15 healthy subjects, 6 females, mean age = 34.3y, SD = 9.8	Prior and 40, 80, 130 and 300 min after psilocybin	3T Siemens Prisma
Gaddis et al. 2022	Psilocybin 10mg/70kg p.o.	Placebo, single-blind, within-subjects	18 healthy subjects, 5 females, mean age = 54.4y, SD = 13.2	100 min after administration	3T Philips Achieva
McCulloch et al. 2022a	Psilocybin 0,2-0,3mg/kg p.o.	Baseline	10 healthy subjects, 4 females, mean age = 28.3y, SD = 3.4 years	15,3+-9,3 days before and one week and 3 months after psilocybin administration	3T Prisma
Madsen et al. 2024	Psilocybin 0,14mg/kg 3 times	Baseline, open label	10 subjects with chronic cluster headache	1 day before the first psilocybin dose and 1 week after the last dose	3T Siemens Prisma
Siegel et al. 2024	Psilocybin 25mg p.o. (Methylphenidate)	Baseline, methylphenidate, randomized cross-over	6 healthy subjects 18-45y	Regular MRI sessions (roughly 18 per participant) before, during (60-180 min following administration), between and after the two drug doses	3T Siemens Prisma

<u>Authors</u>	<u>Substance</u>	<u>Comparator condition, study design</u>	<u>Sample details</u>	<u>Timing of scan</u>	<u>Scanner information</u>
Moujaes et al. 2023	LSD 100µg p.o., psilocybin 0.2mg/kg p.o.	Placebo, double-blind, randomized, crossover design (both substances)	24 healthy subjects, 5 females, mean age = 25.00y; SD = 3.60 (LSD); 23 healthy subjects, 12 males, 11 females, mean age = 26.3y (psilocybin)	75 and 300 min after treatment administration (LSD); 20, 40, and 70 minutes after treatment administration (psilocybin)	3T Philips Achieva
Carhart-Harris et al. 2016	LSD 75µg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects	20 healthy subjects, 4 females, mean age = 30.9y±7.8	60 minutes after infusion	3T GE HDx system
Tagliazucchi et al. 2016	LSD 75µg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects	20 healthy subjects, 4 females, mean age = 30.9y±7.8	60 minutes after infusion	3T GE HDx system
Speth et al. 2016	LSD 75µg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects	20 healthy subjects, 4 females, mean age = 30.9y±7.8 (19 included)	60 minutes after infusion	3T GE HDx system
Müller et al. 2017	LSD 100µg p.o.	Placebo, randomised, double-blind cross-over design	20 participants, 10 females, mean age = 32.4y, SD = 10.9	Scan starting 2.5 h after administration of placebo/LSD	3T Magnetom Prisma, Siemens Healthcare
Müller et al. 2018	LSD 100µg p.o.	Placebo, randomised, double-blind, cross-over trial	20 participants, 10 females, mean age = 32.4y, SD = 10.9	Scan starting 2.5 h after administration of placebo/LSD	3T Magnetom Prisma, Siemens Healthcare
Avram et al. 2022	LSD 100µg p.o.(MDMA, D-amphetamine)	Placebo, double-blind, crossover design with 4 sessions in a random and counterbalanced order	25 healthy subjects, 12 females, mean age = 28.2y, SD = 4.35	Scan starting 2.5 h after administration of placebo/LSD	3T Magnetom Prisma, Siemens Healthcare
Dai et al. 2023	LSD 75µg i.v. (NO, ketamine)	Placebo, within-subjects	15 healthy subjects, 5 females, mean age = 38.4y±8.6	60 minutes after infusion	3T GE HDx system
Delli Pizzi et al. 2023a	LSD 75µg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects	15 healthy subjects, 4 females, mean age = 30.5y ± 8.0	60 minutes after infusion	3T GE HDx system
Delli Pizzi et al. 2023b	LSD 75µg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects	15 healthy subjects, 4 females, mean age = 30.5y ± 8.0	60 minutes after infusion	3T GE HDx system
Shukuroglou et al. 2023	Psilocybin 10mg and 25mg p.o.	Baseline, open label	16 subjects with TRD, 4 female, mean age = 42.75y, SD = 10.15	At baseline and 1 day after second dosing	3T Siemens Tim Trio
Palhano-Fontes et al. 2015	Ayahuasca (2.2 ml/kg containing 0.8 mg/ml of DMT and 0.21 mg/ml of harmine)	Baseline, open label	9 healthy subjects with at least 5 years of regular (twice a month) Ayahuasca use, 5 females, mean age = 29y, 24-48y	Before and 40 min after Ayahuasca intake	1,5T Siemens, Magnetom Vision
Sampedro et al. 2017	Ayahuasca (148±29ml, containing 0.3mg/ml DMT, 0.86mg/ml harmine, 0.17mg/ml tetrahydroharmine, and 0.04mg/ml harmaline)	Baseline, open label	16 healthy subjects with prior ayahuasca experience (previously taken 62 times, SD = 99), 6 females, mean age = 38.9y, SD = 7.8	24 hours prior and 24 hours after the ayahuasca session	3T Siemens Magneto TIM Trio

<u>Authors</u>	<u>Substance</u>	<u>Comparator condition, study design</u>	<u>Sample details</u>	<u>Timing of scan</u>	<u>Scanner information</u>
Pasquini et al. 2020	Ayahuasca (1 ml/kg, containing 0.36mg/ml of N,N-DMT, 1.86mg/ml of harmine, 0.24mg/ml of harmaline, and 1.20mg/ml of tetrahydroharmine)	Placebo, blinded	50 healthy subjects (25 in active group)	1 day before and 24 hours after dosing	1.5T General Electric, HDxt
<u>Effective connectivity</u>					
Kraehenmann et al. 2015a	Psilocybin 0.16 mg/kg p.o.	Placebo, randomized, double-blind, crossover design	25 healthy subjects, 9 females, mean age = 24.2y, SD = 3.42	During task	3T Philips Achieva
Stoliker et al. 2024	Psilocybin 0.2mg/kg p.o.	Placebo, double-blind, randomized, crossover study	23 healthy subjects, 12 males, 11 females, mean age = 26.3y	70 minutes after treatment administration	3T Philips Achieva
Kaelen et al. 2016	LSD 75µg i.v.	Placebo, within-subjects	20 healthy subjects, 4 females, mean age = 30.9y±7.8 (12 included)	60 minutes after infusion	3T GE HDx system, BOLD fMRI
Preller et al. 2019	LSD 100µg p.o.	Placebo/ketanserin, double-blind, randomized, crossover design	25 healthy subjects, 6 females, mean age = 25.24y, SD = 3.72	75 min and 300 min after treatment administration	3T Philips Achieva
Stoliker et al. 2023	LSD 100µg p.o.	Placebo, double-blind, randomized, crossover study	25 healthy subjects, 6 females, mean age = 25.24y, SD = 3.72	75 min and 300 min after treatment administration	3T Philips Achieva
Avram et al. 2023	LSD 100µg p.o. (MDMA, D-amphetamine)	Placebo, double-blind, crossover design with 4 sessions in a random and counterbalanced order	25 healthy subjects, 12 females, mean age = 28.2y, SD = 4.35	Scan starting 2.5 h after administration of placebo/LSD	3T Magnetom Prisma, Siemens Healthcare
Bedford et al. 2023	LSD 100µg p.o.	Placebo, randomised, double-blind, cross-over trial	20 healthy subjects, 10 females, mean age = 32.4y, SD = 10.9	Scan starting 2.5 h after administration of placebo/LSD	3T Magnetom Prisma, Siemens Healthcare
<u>Task-based fMRI - activation studies</u>					
Carhart-Harris et al. 2012b	Psilocybin 2 mg i.v.	Placebo, within-subject	15 healthy subjects, 13 males and 2 females, mean age = 32y	60 s infusion exactly 6 min after the start of the 12 min scan	3T GE HDx system, BOLD fMRI
Kraehenmann et al. 2015b	Psilocybin 0.16 mg/kg p.o.	Placebo, randomized, double-blind, crossover design	25 healthy subjects, 9 females, mean age = 24.2y, SD = 3.42	During task	3T Philips Achieva
Preller et al. 2016	Psilocybin 0.215mg/kg p.o.	Placebo, randomized, double-blind, within-subject	21 healthy subjects, 9 females, mean age = 26.48y, SD = 4.76	During task	3T Philips Achieva

<u>Authors</u>	<u>Substance</u>	<u>Comparator condition, study design</u>	<u>Sample details</u>	<u>Timing of scan</u>	<u>Scanner information</u>
Roseman et al. 2018	Psilocybin 10mg and 25mg p.o.	Baseline, open label trial	16 subjects with TRD, 4 female, mean age = 42.75y, SD = 10.15	At baseline and 1 day after second dosing	3T Siemens Tim Trio
Barrett et al. 2020a	Psilocybin 25mg/70kg p.o.	Baseline, open-label	12 healthy subjects, 7 females, mean age = 32.1y, SD = 7.5	One day before, one week after, and one month after psilocybin administration	3T Philips
Mertens et al. 2020	Psilocybin 10mg and 25mg p.o.	Baseline, open label trial	16 subjects with TRD, 4 female, mean age = 42.75y, SD = 10.15	At baseline and 1 day after second dosing	3T Siemens Tim Trio
Duerler et al. 2022	Psilocybin 0.2 mg/kg p.o.	Placebo, double-blind, randomized, crossover design	15 healthy subjects, 5 females, mean age = 26.86y	85 minutes after psilocybin/placebo administration	3T Philips Achieva
Pagni et al. 2024	Psilocybin 25mg/70 kg p.o.	Placebo-controlled	14 subjects with alcohol use disorder (6 in psilocybin group)	2–3 days before and 1–2 days after receiving the first dose of study blinded medication	3T Siemens Skyra
Mueller et al. 2017	LSD 100µg p.o.	Placebo, randomised, double-blind, cross-over design	20 healthy subjects	Scan starting 2.5 h after administration of placebo/LSD	3T Magnetom Prisma, Siemens Healthcare
Preller et al. 2017	LSD 100µg p.o.	Placebo/ketanserin, double-blind, randomized, crossover design	22 healthy subjects, 5 females, mean age = 25.68y, SD = 3.67	Scan 100 min after treatment with placebo or LSD	3T Philips Achieva
Preller et al. 2018a	LSD 100µg p.o.	Placebo/ketanserin, double-blind, randomized, crossover design	24 healthy subjects, 6 females, mean age= 25.42y, SD= 3.6	Task conducted 310 min after treatment administration	3T Philips Achieva
Schmidt et al. 2018	LSD 100µg p.o.	Placebo, randomised, double-blind, cross-over design	18 healthy subjects, 9 females, mean age = 31y, SD = 9	Task conducted 200 min after drug administration	3T Siemens Magnetom Verio
Duerler et al. 2020	LSD 100µg p.o.	Placebo/ketanserin, double-blind, randomized, crossover design	24 healthy subjects, 6 females, mean age= 25.25y, SD= 3.72	Task conducted 330 min after treatment administration	3T Philips Achieva
de Araujo et al. 2011	Ayahuasca (2.2 ml/kg containing 0.8 mg/ml of DMT and 0.21 mg/ml of harmine)	Baseline, open label	9 healthy subjects, frequent Ayahuasca users, 5 females, mean age = 29y (24 to 48y)	Before and 40 minutes after ayahuasca intake	1,5T Siemens Magnetom Vision
Arruda Sanchez et al. 2024	Ayahuasca (30ml/70kg, corresponding to 0.333mg/kg DMT, 0.473mg/kg Harmine, 0.023mg/kg Harmaline, and 0.470mg/kg THH)	Baseline, open label	19 healthy subjects, experienced Ayahuasca users, all males, mean age = 31.5y, SD = 10.7	Before and 50 minutes after ayahuasca ingestion	1,5T Siemens Magnetom Avanto

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Fig. 1: PRISMA flow diagram for study selection and exclusion process

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Fig. 2: Schematic summary of major findings of effective connectivity changes

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Blue neurons represent decreases in EC, red neurons represent increases in EC, pink neurons represent change from inhibitory EC to excitatory. The direction of effective connectivity is represented by the arrow. Study with music not shown. A amygdala, C cortex, DMN default mode network, PCC posterior cingular cortex, PVC primary visual cortex, SN salience network, SV striatum ventrale, T thalamus, TMC transmodal cortex, UMC unimodal cortex.

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